

Clinicopathological Profile of Appendectomy Specimens: A Hospital Based Retrospective Study from a Teaching Hospital, Odisha.

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Abstract:

Background: To investigate the pathological variations in appendectomy specimens and identify potential demographic associations, a retrospective analysis was performed focusing on: (1) the range of histopathological diagnoses, (2) patient characteristics linked to these diagnoses, and (3) the incidence of ruptured appendices, unnecessary surgeries (negative appendectomy rate), and unexpected pathology discovered during appendectomy.

Materials and Methods: The clinicopathological details of patients who underwent appendectomy at Shri Jagannath Medical College and Hospital, Puri, between January 2022 and December 2023 were reviewed retrospectively.

Results: There were 214 cases found to have histopathology proven appendicitis among which 129 (60.2%) males and 85 (39.7%) females with the male: female ratio of 1.5:1. The mean age for male was 28.9 ±11.3 yrs with a range of 1 to 68 yrs and for female was 31.7±7.08 yrs with a range of 2 to 71 yrs and the mean age for The peak age incidence of appendicitis was found in the age group of 21 to 30 years. More than 90% cases of appendicitis occurred below the age of 40 years. Most of the positive appendicitis cases 58 (45.0%) were reported as acute appendicitis in the final histopathology report. Acute appendicitis showed a peak incidence among patients aged 11 to 30 years. Conversely, chronic, recurrent, resolving, and eosinophilic appendicitis were more prevalent in the 21 to 40 year age group. Acute appendicitis and perforated appendicitis was seen more commonly in females at the age interval of 11-30 yrs.

Conclusion: Appendicitis is most common in young adults, slightly more frequent in males. Laparoscopy during appendectomy in women helps identify unsuspected pelvic issues, lowering unnecessary surgeries. Examining appendix tissue post-surgery is crucial to avoid missing other problems. Surgeons should recognize rare appendix pathologies that may require further treatment. Effective management of appendix issues requires considering clinical details, imaging (CT scans), and tissue analysis.

Key words: Appendectomy; Appendicitis; Histopathology.

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Introduction

Acute appendicitis, a frequent surgical emergency throughout life (7% lifetime risk), primarily affects adolescents and young adults. Interestingly, the incidence varies geographically. Studies report a decline in developed countries like the US and UK, whereas developing countries show an increase, possibly linked to dietary changes [1,2,3,4].

Even with advancements in technology and imaging techniques, accurately diagnosing acute appendicitis remains a challenge. Histopathological examination, the microscopic analysis of tissue samples, continues to be the definitive method for confirming appendicitis. This method not only identifies acute inflammation but can also reveal unexpected

findings like tumors in the appendix, further emphasizing the importance of examining every single appendix removed during surgery.

This study investigates the spectrum of histologic diagnoses in surgically resected appendices. We further aim to analyze the association between age, sex, and the following: incidence of appendicitis, perforation rate, negative appendectomy rate, and rate of incidental findings.

Materials and Methods

The clinicopathological details of patients who underwent appendectomy at Shri Jagannath Medical College and Hospital, Puri, between January 2022

and December 2023 were reviewed retrospectively. Histopathological details of all surgically resected appendices submitted to histopathological analysis were included in this study. All emergency and interval appendectomies performed on patients with clinically suspected appendicitis. Incidental appendectomies performed during other abdominal or pelvic surgeries. Relevant clinical data, gross findings, and histopathological diagnoses were retrieved from the patient file. Negative appendectomy was defined as one which is performed for a clinical diagnosis of acute appendicitis but in which the appendix is found to be normal on histopathological examination.

Results

There were 214 cases found to have histopathology proven appendicitis among which 129 (60.2%) males and 85 (39.7%) females with the male: female ratio of 1.5:1. The mean age for male was 28.9 ± 11.3 yrs with a range of 1 to 68 yrs and for female was 31.7 ± 7.08 yrs with a range of 2 to 71 yrs and the mean age for The peak age incidence of appendicitis was found in the age group of 21 to 30 years. More than 90% cases of appendicitis occurred below the age of 40 years (Table 1) (Graph 1).

Table 1: Age and sex wise distribution of study population.

Age Group	Total (N=214)		Male(129)		Female (85,)	
	n	%	n	%	n	%
<10	3	1.4	2	1.6	1	1.2
11-20	61	28.5	36	27.9	25	29.4
21-30	92	43.0	58	45.0	34	40.0
31-40	45	21.0	29	22.5	16	18.8
41-50	7	3.3	2	1.6	5	5.9
51-60	4	1.9	2	1.6	2	2.4
>61	2	0.9	0	0.0	2	2.4

Figure 1 Age and sex wise distribution of patients underwent appendectomy

Our data showed that most of the positive appendicitis cases 58 (45.0%) were reported as acute appendicitis in the final histopathology report (Table 2).

Table 2. Sex wise distribution of appendicitis.

Histological stages	Male (N=129)		Female (N=85)		Total (N=214)	
	n	%	n	%	n	%
Acute appendicitis	58	45.0	48	56.5	106	49.5
Acute suppurative appendicitis	36	27.9	16	18.8	52	24.3
Acute gangrenous appendicitis	27	20.9	14	16.5	41	19.2
Perforated appendicitis	2	1.6	3	3.5	5	2.3
Eosinophilic appendicitis	1	0.8	2	2.4	3	1.4
Chronic/ resolving/recurrent appendicitis	5	3.9	3	3.5	8	3.7

Acute appendicitis showed a peak incidence among patients aged 11 to 30 years. Conversely, chronic,

recurrent, resolving, and eosinophilic appendicitis were more prevalent in the 21 to 40 year age group.

Acute appendicitis and perforated appendicitis was seen more commonly in females at the age interval of 11-30 yrs.

Some of the clinically suspicious appendicitis which was proven to be appendicitis later by microscopic examination had other associated histologic findings. These included normal appendix with no inflammatory changes, followed by granulomas, endosalpingiosis of appendix, broad ligament cyst, mesenteric cyst.

There were total 13 cases of incidental appendectomy of which 4 were males and 9 were females. The most common primary surgery was total abdominal hysterectomy with bilateral salpingo-oophorectomy (7 cases) followed by oophorectomy with or without adenectomy (2 cases), GI surgery (3 cases; 1 female, 3 males) and one emergency exploratory laparotomy (1 female).

Discussion

Acute appendicitis has been the most prevalent surgical emergency for decades, necessitating appendectomy as the most commonly performed abdominal surgery. Within the Western world, it accounts for roughly 40% of all surgical emergencies. While historically less frequent in Asian and African subcontinents, recent literature reviews suggest a potential rise in appendicitis incidence within India. This trend might be attributed to the growing adoption of Western dietary patterns and lifestyles [4].

This study confirms a higher prevalence of appendicitis in males compared to females, with a male-to-female ratio of 1.5:1 [5, 6]. Consistent with prior research, the incidence peaked in the second and third decades of life, with approximately 80% of cases occurring in individuals under 40 years old [7,8]. Furthermore, our findings align with previous studies reporting a male predominance in appendicitis, particularly during adolescence [9].

Consistent with prior research, our analysis of histologically diagnosed appendicitis cases revealed a predominance of acute appendicitis (45.6%), followed by acute suppurative (20.8%) and gangrenous appendicitis (16.3%). These findings were consistent with previous reports [5, 9, 10].

Similar to Nabipour et al., [11] who observed a weak association between histological severity and patient demographics, our study found no significant influence of age on the incidence of appendicitis across various histological stages in young adults (10-30 years old). However, sex distribution differed based on the histological subtype. Males exhibited a greater prevalence of acute suppurative and gangrenous appendicitis, while females had a higher prevalence of acute and perforated forms of the disease. These findings align with previous research [9].

Our study revealed a higher prevalence of eosinophilic and chronic/recurrent/resolving appendicitis

in females and a slightly older age group. The observed frequency of eosinophilic appendicitis (0.8%) aligns closely with the 1% incidence reported by Park et al., [12]. However, the diagnosis of chronic/recurrent/resolving appendicitis remains a topic of debate. Several researchers posit a potential link between chronic pelvic pain and chronic appendiceal inflammation. In some cases, appendectomy performed in patients with a normal pelvic anatomy has reportedly shown a 50% reduction in pain [13, 14]. Within our study cohort, the prevalence of chronic/recurrent/resolving appendicitis reached 2.5% across both young and older adults, exceeding the rates reported in some other studies [14]. Therefore, recurrent abdominal pain warrants careful evaluation. Maintaining a high clinical suspicion for appendicitis is essential to minimize unnecessary and repeated hospital admissions.

This study found a low perforation rate (1.6%) in perforated appendicitis cases, consistent with rates reported in previous study [11]. However, some studies have documented significantly higher perforation rates, ranging from 8.3% to 23.2% [3, 15]. Interestingly, our study revealed a distinct age distribution for perforated appendicitis compared to previous investigations [15, 16]. We observed a higher prevalence of perforation within the 20-40 year age group, whereas most other studies reported higher rates at the extremes of age. This difference might be explained by earlier presentation to the hospital in our study cohort, allowing surgeons to make timely surgical decisions for suspected appendicitis.

The potential role of parasitic infestation in appendicitis etiology has been a topic of discussion. Several studies have documented the presence of luminal parasites in the appendix, in both appendicitis and non-appendicitis cases, at a rate of 0.3% to 3.15% [17, 18]. *Enterobius vermicularis* and *Schistosoma* species are the most frequently encountered parasites. In our own investigation, eight cases exhibited parasitic infestation. Three of these cases presented with unidentified parasites within the lumen of chronically inflamed appendices, and another case was suggestive of parasitic involvement due to foreign body reaction and transmural eosinophilic infiltration.

When an appendectomy reveals no signs of inflammation, a variety of unexpected abnormalities can be found under a microscope (histopathological findings). These findings include tumors (carcinoid tumor, mucinous neoplasms, adenocarcinoma), infections (tuberculosis, actinomycosis, *Enterobius vermicularis*), inflammations (granulomatous inflammation), misplaced tissue (appendiceal endometriosis), and structural changes (eosinophilic infiltration, appendicular diverticulitis) [9,10,19]. In our study, the most common finding in negative appendicitis was a normal appendix with no inflammation. Other findings included granulomas, tissue from the

fallopian tube lining the appendix (endosalpingiosis), and cysts in the supporting tissue (broad ligament cyst, mesenteric cyst).

Studies show women are more likely to undergo unnecessary appendectomies than men [11, 17, 20]. This is likely because some gynecological problems in women can mimic appendicitis symptoms, such as ovarian cysts, tumors, and endometriosis [21]. Similarly, in this study, most negative appendectomies were in women, and the culprit might be a non-inflamed tumor causing pain through inflammatory chemicals.

The preceding discussion clearly demonstrates that sending all appendectomy specimens for histological evaluation is both mandatory and advantageous. When we weigh the cost of the procedure against the potential benefits, it becomes evident that the benefits in this case far outweigh the cost. Early detection and management of an appendicular lesion can save the patient from incurring additional expenses if the disease progresses to involve other organs.

Conclusion

Appendicitis is most common in young adults, slightly more frequent in males. Laparoscopy during appendectomy in women helps identify unsuspected pelvic issues, lowering unnecessary surgeries. Examining appendix tissue post-surgery is crucial to avoid missing other problems. Surgeons should recognize rare appendix pathologies that may require further treatment. Effective management of appendix issues requires considering clinical details, imaging (CT scans), and tissue analysis.

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